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A NUMERICAL METHOD FOR VARIABLE-ORDER FRACTIONAL PANTOGRAPH DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS BASED ON MITTAG-LEFFLER POLYNOMIALS

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ABSTRACT. The main aim of this study is to develop Mittag-Leffler polynomials (MLPs) for solving variable order fractional pantograph differential equations. For the MLPs, we obtain the operational matrix of Caputo's variable order derivative. We also introduced pantograph operational matrix of MLPs. The equations under concern in this study can be turned into algebraic equations with unknown MLPs coefficients. The superiority of the current approach is demonstrated with some examples, and the results indicate its good results.

1. INTRODUCTION AND PRELIMINARIES

Variable order fractional calculus is the study of derivative and integral operators whose orders allowed the use of any known function. This property provides more sensitive and accurate modeling of practical issues in science and engineering [1]. We consider the general form of variable order fractional pantograph differential equations:

$$\begin{cases} D^{\nu(t)}u(t) = \mathcal{F}(t, u(t), u(\delta t), D^{\beta(t)}u(\delta t)), & t \in [0, 1], \quad \nu(t), \beta(t) \in (0, 1] \\ u(0) = u_0. \end{cases} \quad (1.1)$$

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where \mathcal{F} is smooth functions and δ denotes the pantograph element. Here, we propose a new numerical algorithm to solve the mentioned problem based on MLPs and collocation method.

2. DESCRIPTION OF NUMERICAL METHOD

Here, using the derivative operational matrix of MLPs, we examine the approximation of the solution to the given problems. MLPs are defined as the following form [3]

$$M_n(t) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (n-1)_{n-k} 2^k (t)_k, \quad (2.1)$$

where $(t)_n$ is a falling factorial.

Remark 2.1. According to the Vieta's formulas, the following property is established for $(t)_n$ [3].

$$(t)_n = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} A_k t^k. \quad (2.2)$$

An arbitrary function $u(t) \in L^2[0, 1]$ can be approximated as follows

$$f(t) \simeq \sum_{n=0}^N c_n M_n(t) = C^T M(t), \quad (2.3)$$

where C and $M(t)$ are $(N+1) \times 1$ vectors. Also, we have $M(t) = BX_t$, where $X_t = [1, t, t^2, \dots, t^N]$ and $B = [b_{i,j}]$.

Lemma 2.2. *The matrix that represents Caputo's variable-order derivative's effect on the coefficients of the MLPs in Eq. (2.3) is given by*

$$D^{\nu(t)} f(t) = I^{1-\nu(t)} \frac{d}{dt} f(t) \simeq C^T \tilde{\mu}_t^\nu X_t, \quad (2.4)$$

where $\tilde{\mu}_t^\nu = BD_t \mu_t^\nu$, D_t is derivative operational matrix of Taylor polynomials [2].

$$\mu_t^\nu = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{t^{1-\nu(t)}\Gamma(1)}{\Gamma(2-\nu(t))} & 0 & \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{t^{1-\nu(t)}\Gamma(2)}{\Gamma(3-\nu(t))} & \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{t^{1-\nu(t)}\Gamma(m+1)}{\Gamma(m+2-\nu(t))} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & \frac{t^{1-\nu(t)}\Gamma(N+1)}{\Gamma(N+2-\nu(t))} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.5)$$

□

Now, we present the procedure for obtaining a pantograph operational matrix for MLPs.

$$M(\delta t) \simeq D^{(\delta)} M(t), \quad 0 < \delta < 1, \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1, \quad (2.6)$$

where, the matrix $D^{(\delta)}$ is the pantograph operational matrix of MLPs. As the first step, for $n = 0$, we have

$$M_0(\delta t) = M_0(t) = 2. \tag{2.7}$$

For $n \geq 1$, using Eq. (2.3), we get

$$M_n(\delta t) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (n-1)_{(n-k)} 2^k (\delta t)^k. \tag{2.8}$$

Using Eq. (2.2), we achieve [3]

$$M_n(\delta t) = \sum_{k=0}^n c_{l,k} t^k, \tag{2.9}$$

where

$$c_{l,k} = \sum_{l=0}^{n-1} \binom{n}{k} (n-1)_{(n-k)} 2^k \delta^l A_l. \tag{2.10}$$

Now, using the above relations, substituting Eqs. (2.4) and (2.9) in equation (1.1), we derive

$C^T \tilde{\mu}_t^\nu X_t \simeq \mathcal{F}(t, C^T A X_t, C^T A D_\delta X_t, C^T \tilde{\mu}_t^\delta D_\delta X_t)$,
with initial condition $C^T A X_t(0) = u_0$. By solving the proposed system by taking the collocation points $t_i = \frac{i}{N+1}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, the approximate solution is obtained.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND ILLUSTRATIVE TEST PROBLEMS

In this section, we study variable order fractional pantograph derivative to illustrate the efficiency and accuracy of the suggested technique.

Example 3.1. Consider the following equation [1]:

$$D^{\nu(t)} u(t) = \frac{1}{2} u(t) + \frac{1}{2} e^{\frac{t}{2}} u\left(\frac{t}{2}\right), \quad u(0) = 1, \quad t \in [0, 10], \quad \nu(t) \in (0, 1]. \tag{3.1}$$

The exact solution to this problem when $\nu(t) = 1$ is $u(t) = \exp(t)$. In Figure 1, we display the approximate solution and the absolute error for various $\nu(t)$ values with $N = 8$. These results demonstrate that the strategy gives precise results.

Example 3.2. Consider the variable-order fractional pantograph differential equation [1]:

$$D_t^{\nu(t)} u(t) = -u(t) + \frac{1}{10} u\left(\frac{4t}{5}\right) + \frac{1}{2} D_t^{\beta(t)} u\left(\frac{4t}{5}\right) + \left(\frac{6}{25} t - \frac{2}{5}\right) e^{-\frac{4}{5}t} + e^{-t}, \tag{3.2}$$

$t \in [0, 10], \quad u(0) = 0.$

The exact solution to this problem in the case when $\nu(t) = \beta(t) = 1$ is $u(t) = t \exp(t)$. The presented method with $N = 8$ is used to solve this problem for some choices $\nu(t)$ and $\beta(t)$. We approximate the solution by using the proposed method corresponding to different values of fractional variable order as in Figure 2.

FIGURE 1. The approximate solution for different functions of $\nu(t)$ (left) and the absolute error for $\nu(t) = 1$ (right) with $N = 8$ of Example 1.

FIGURE 2. Diagrams of the approximate solutions for some selections $\nu(t)$ and $\beta(t) = 1$ (left) and the $\nu(t) = 1$ and different values of $\beta(t)$ (right) with $N = 8$ for Example 2.

4. CONCLUSION

The goal of this study was to develop an accurate approach for solving variable order fractional pantograph differential equations based on Mittag-Leffler polynomials. To design the computational method, we presented operational matrix of Caputo's variable order derivative and pantograph operational matrix of MLPs. Then, using the mentioned matrices and the collocation approach, the problem was transformed into a system of algebraic equations. The operational matrices had a lot of zero components that cause little CPU time, implementing this method was very convenient and effective because of a simple algorithm. The present method has been applied to several examples and was compared to some other methods showing that this method is more accurate.

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